

Diphenylamine-2-carboxylic acids (I) (R = H, 2-CH₃, 3-CH₃, 4-CH₃) were obtained according to the published procedure¹⁷⁻²⁰.

Diphenylamine-2-carboxylic acid hydrazides (III, Table 1):

An intimate mixture of diphenylamine-2-carboxylic acid (20.0 g.), thionyl chloride (20.0 ml) and absolute methanol (250 ml) was refluxed for 12-15 hrs. Thereafter excess of methanol was distilled off. The contents of the flask were cooled, diluted with 250 ml of water and neutralised with sodium carbonate at 5°-10°. The crude ester thus obtained was filtered and used without further purification.

Hydrazine hydrate 95% (0.2 mole), II (0.1 mole) and 50 ml of methanol were taken in a 500 ml round bottomed flask. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 12 hrs. Excess of methanol was removed in vacuum and the crude hydrazide was recrystallised from ethanol or dilute ethanol.

N-Benzylidenediphenylamine-2-carboxylic acid hydrazides (IV, Table 2):

Equimolar amounts of hydrazide (III) and a suitable aldehyde were suspended in 20 ml of ethanol. The reaction mixture was heated on a steam bath for 1 hr. The crude product thus separated was recrystallised from a suitable solvent.

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References

1. T. RINDERSPACHER and B. PRIJS, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1958, 41, 22.
2. A. WINTERSTEIN, B. HEGEDUS, B. FUST, E. BOHNI and A. STUDER, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1956, 39, 229.
3. W. WERNER, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1953, 18, 1333.
4. A. L. MINDZHOYAN, *Arm. Khim. Zh.*, 1966, 19, 793; *Chem. Abs.*, 1967, 67, 539432.
5. O. ISLER, H. GUTMANN, O. STRAUB, B. FUST, E. BOHNI and A. STUDER, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1955, 38, 1033, 1046.
6. K. U. M. PRASAD, B. H. IYER and M. SIRSI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1966, 43, 784.
7. S. S. PARMAR and R. KUMAR, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1968, 11, 635.
8. V. S. MISRA and R. S. VARMA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1962, 39, 763.
9. T. S. GARDENER, E. WENIS and J. LEE, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1961, 26, 1514.
10. SWISS, 419,136, 1967, *Chem. Abs.*, 1968, 68, 29709c.

11. A. ALEMANY, M. BERNABÉ, E. F. ALVAREZ, M. LOBA-TAMAYO and O. NIETO, *Bull. Soc. Chim. (France)*, 1967, 780.
12. D. LIEBERMANN and J.-c. RENIS, *Bull. Soc. Chim. (France)*, 1961, 1952.
13. M. H. WEINSWIG and E. B. ROCHE, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 1965, 54, 1216.
14. R. CAVIER and R. RIPS, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1965, 8, 706.
15. BRIT. 1,085,474, 1967; *Chem. Abs.*, 1968, 68, 95567f.
16. R. S. VARMA and S. A. IMAM, *Indian J. Microbiol.*, 1973, 13, 45.
17. A. T. VOGEL, "Practical Organic Chemistry", Third Edition, Longman Group Ltd., London, 1971, p. 991.
18. K. LEHMSTEDT, W. BURNS and H. KLEE, *Ber.*, 1936, 69B, 2399.
19. K. LEHMSTEDT and SCHRADER, *Ber.*, 1937, 70, 838.
20. ULLMANN and BADER, *Ann.*, 1907, 355, 323.
21. A. ALBERT, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 1225.

Use of *p*-Dimethyl Amino Anil of Anthracene Glyoxal as Gravimetric Reagent in the Determination of Platinum and Palladium

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IN our previous communication¹ *p*-dimethyl amino anil of 3-phenanthryl glyoxal was used as gravimetric reagent for platinum in acetonic medium. *P*-dimethyl amino anil of anthracene glyoxal² has been found a good complexing reagent for large number of transition metals². During the complexometric investigations, it has been observed that reagent reacts quantitatively with Pt(IV) and Pd(II) in acetone. Gravimetric estimations of Pt(IV) and Pd(II) with the reagent and effect of various compounds has been thought worthwhile from analytical view point.

Preparation of the solution: Reagent was dissolved in doubly distilled acetone to prepare approximately 0.01M solution. Stock solutions of metal chlorides (J.M.) were prepared in acetone and were standardised gravimetrically³.

Precipitating reagent was slowly added, with constant stirring, to the known volume (05-50 ml) of metal chloride which was prediluted to 25-100 ml. After allowing to stand for 15-20 mins, precipitate was filtered through sintered glass crucible; washed 2-3 times with dry acetone and ether successively; dried in oven and was weighed as Pt(C₂₄H₂₀N₂O)₂Cl₄.

NOTES

and $\text{Pd}(\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_2\text{O})\text{Cl}_2$. Colours of the complexes were dark grey and brown respectively. Several experiments were performed by using different volumes of each metal chloride solutions.

From the results it is concluded that reagent *p*-dimethyl amino anil of anthracene glyoxal is an effective gravimetric reagent for Pt(IV) and Pd(II). In the gravimetric experiments error was found of the order 0.2 to 1.0 and 0.5 to 1.5% respectively. Both the complexes were insoluble in aqueous acetic acid, ether, benzene, carbon tetrachloride and water. This method may be regarded of limited applicability as has been tried only in the acetonic medium. Reagent is quite effective and specific in the presence of NiCl_2 , CuCl_2 , CuBr , FeCl_3 , MnCl_2 , $\text{Cu}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2$, AgNO_3 , SmCl_3 , LaCl_3 and YCl_3 .

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References

1. R. K. UPADHYAY, R. C. SAXENA and R. PRASAD, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1973, 50, 158.
2. P. SINGH, Ph.D. Thesis, Meerut Univ., 1971.
3. A. I. VOGEL, "A Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", Longman Group Limited, London, 1969.

Effect of Different Nitrogenous Fertilizers and Lime on the Availability of Manganese in Acid Soils

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MANGANESE is recognised as one of the trace elements in plant nutrition. There had been different indices for available manganese in soil¹. Water soluble plus exchangeable manganese is considered as available for plants². Easily reducible manganese is also considered as active which may be slowly available to plants. Active manganese status in soils depends upon a number of factors such as *pH*, mineralisation of organic matter, oxidation reduction potential in soils etc.³ Nitrogen and sulphur additions were shown to beneficially affect its availability to arable crops⁴. It is sometimes feared that acid producing nitrogenous fertilizers, especially those producing acidity even by hydrolysis, may increase the available manganese in acid soils to an extent of damaging crops by manganese toxicity. In view of that the present investigation was undertaken to study the effect of three nitrogenous fertilizers, *viz.* ammonium sulphate, urea and calcium nitrate,

which differ in their acid producing ability, on the available manganese status in acid soils. The effect of liming on manganese availability was also studied.

Experimental

Three different acid soils (two from North Bengal *i.e.*, Naxalbari and Raidak and one from Birbhum District, Sriniketan) of West Bengal were collected. The relevant physico-chemical properties of the soils are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—PHYSICO-CHEMICAL PROPERTIES OF THE SOILS

Properties	Soils		
	Naxalbari	Raidak	Sriniketan
<i>pH</i> (Soil : Water = 1 : 2)	5.5	4.6	5.2
Organic carbon (%)	1.07	1.59	0.65
C.E.C. (me/100 g)	10.8	17.0	8.0
Clay (%)	39.6	25.1	32.6

The soil samples (10 g.) were incubated for 15 days at $30^\circ \pm 1^\circ$ with moisture at 50% moisture holding capacity with the treatments (1) control, (2) ammonium sulphate, (3) urea, and (4) calcium nitrate at the rate of 200 lbs/N/acre and (5) lime to raise the soil *pH* initially to 6.8 to 7.0. Calcium oxide was used as the liming material. All the chemicals used were analytical grade. Water soluble, exchangeable and reducible manganese were extracted and determined by the method as described by Jackson⁵. The analyses were made in duplicate and the mean values have been presented in the Table 2.

TABLE 2—*pH* OF THE SOILS AFTER 15 DAYS OF INCUBATION

Treatments	Soils		
	Naxalbari	Raidak	Sriniketan
Control	5.8	4.9	5.3
Ammonium sulphate	5.4	4.6	4.9
Urea	5.7	5.2	5.2
Calcium nitrate	5.6	4.8	5.2
Lime	6.5	5.6	6.1

Results and Discussion

The *pH* of the incubated soils has been shown in Table 2 and the results of the effect of different treatments on various forms of soil manganese have been presented in Table 3.

The addition of the nitrogenous fertilizers led to an increase in water soluble manganese and it was found that the application of calcium nitrate released greatest quantity of manganese followed by ammonium sulphate and urea. The same sequence was